

DESCRIPTION OF LOCAL AND 2-LOCAL INNER DERIVATIONS OF FIVE-DIMENSIONAL JORDAN ALGEBRAS

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Abstract. *In this article we studied and described inner derivations, local and 2-local inner derivations of five-dimensional nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras. We also gave a criterion of a linear operator on these Jordan algebras to be a local inner derivation.*

Key words: *Jordan algebra, derivation, local derivation, inner derivation, local inner derivation, nilpotent algebra.*

Introduction. Jordan algebras are classical algebras widely studied by specialists. Jordan algebras turned out to be related to other classical algebras such as associative algebras and Lie algebras. The classification of finite-dimensional Jordan algebras is one of the primary areas of modern algebra and, as is known, was first studied by P. Jordan, J. von Neumann and E. Wigner [1]. Classifications of 3- and 4-dimensional Jordan algebras were given by I. Kashuba and M.E. Martin in [2] and M.E. Martin in [3], respectively. Moreover, nilpotent Jordan algebras of dimension five were classified by Hegazy and Abdwahab [4]. Most classification problems for finite-dimensional Jordan algebras have been studied in order to establish certain properties of Jordan algebras, while the complete classification of Jordan algebras in general is still an open problem. There are many theoretical works on derivations and inner derivations of associative and Lie algebras, see [5], [6], [7] and [8] respectively. However, in the case of Jordan algebras, there are few of them. For this reason, our interest in this article lies in the study and description of inner derivations of five-dimensional Jordan algebras.

In the present article, we study local derivations of five-dimensional Jordan algebras. The concept of local derivation goes back to the Gleason-Kahane-Zelazko theorem, which is a fundamental contribution to the theory of Banach algebras. This theorem asserts that every unital linear functional F on a complex unital Banach algebra A such that $F(a)$ belongs to the spectrum $\sigma(a)$ of the operator a for every $a \in A$, is multiplicative (cf. [9], [10]). In modern terminology, this is equivalent to the following condition: any unital linear local homomorphism from a unital complex Banach algebra A to the field \mathbb{C} of complex numbers is multiplicative. Recall that a linear mapping T from a Banach algebra A to a Banach algebra B is called a local homomorphism if for every a in A there exists a homomorphism $\Phi_a: A \rightarrow B$, depending on a such that $T(a) = \Phi_a(a)$.

A similar notion was introduced and studied to characterize derivations on operator algebras. Namely, the concept of local derivations was introduced by R. Kadison [11] and D. Larson, A. Surur [12] independently in 1990. A linear mapping ∇ of an algebra A into itself is a local derivation if for each a in A there exists a derivation D_a on A such that $D_a(a) = \nabla(a)$.

1 Preliminary information

In this section, we provide the necessary terminology and notations that will be needed to present this scientific work.

Definition. A Jordan algebra \mathcal{J} is a vector space over a field F equipped with a bilinear operator $\cdot : \mathcal{J} \times \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$, satisfying the following identities:

$$x \cdot y = y \cdot x, (x^2 \cdot y) \cdot x = x^2 \cdot (y \cdot x) \quad (1)$$

for any $x, y \in \mathcal{J}$. An important special case of mappings is the so-called "derivation". In this section, we introduce the notion of inner derivations of Jordan algebras and give their properties.

Let \mathcal{J} be a Jordan algebra. Recall that a linear map $D: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is called a derivation if $D(xy) = D(x)y + xD(y)$ for any two elements $x, y \in \mathcal{J}$.

A linear mapping $\nabla: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is called a local derivation if for every $x \in \mathcal{J}$ there exists a derivation $D: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ such that $\nabla(x) = D(x)$.

A map $\Delta: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ is called a 2-local derivation, if for any two elements $x, y \in \mathcal{J}$ there exists a derivation $D_{x,y}: \mathcal{J} \rightarrow \mathcal{J}$ such that $\Delta(x) = D_{x,y}(x), \Delta(y) = D_{x,y}(y)$.

2 Inner derivations and local inner derivations on five-dimensional nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras

In this section, we describe inner derivations of the five-dimensional Jordan algebras in Table 1. The following theorem takes place.

Theorem: *Inner derivations and local inner derivations of the five-dimensional nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras are described as in the following table:*

Table 1. Inner derivations and local inner derivations on five-dimensional nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras.

\mathcal{J}	General form of a inner derivation	General form of a local inner derivation	Is each local inner derivation a inner derivation?	Is each 2-local inner derivation a inner derivation?
\mathcal{J}_1	$\{E_{3,1}\}$	$\{E_{3,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_2	$\{E_{3,1} + E_{3,4}\}$	$\{E_{3,1}, E_{3,4}\}$	-	+
\mathcal{J}_3	$\{E_{3,1} + E_{3,4}\}$	$\{E_{3,1}, E_{3,4}\}$	-	+
\mathcal{J}_4	$\{E_{3,4}\}$	$\{E_{3,4}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_5	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_6	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_7	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	-
\mathcal{J}_8	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	-
\mathcal{J}_9	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	-
\mathcal{J}_{10}	$\{E_{5,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_{11}	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_{12}	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_{13}	$\{E_{5,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_{14}	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
\mathcal{J}_{15}^α	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+

J_{16}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	+	—
J_{17}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	+	—
J_{18}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,3}\}$	+	—
J_{19}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	—
J_{20}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	—
J_{21}	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	+	—
J_{22}	$\{E_{5,3}\}$	$\{E_{5,3}\}$	+	+
J_{23}^β	$\{\beta E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	$\{\beta E_{5,1}, E_{5,2}\}$	—	+
J_{24}^γ	$\{(\gamma - 1)E_{5,1}\}$	$\{(\gamma - 1)E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
J_{24}^0	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
$J_{24}^{\frac{1}{2}}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
J_{25}	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	$\{E_{5,1}\}$	+	+
J_{26}^δ	$\{E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
J_{26}^0	$\{E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
$J_{27}^{\varepsilon, \phi}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
$J_{27}^{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-1}}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
$J_{27}^{-1, -1}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	$\{-E_{5,1} + E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
J_{28}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{29}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{30}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{31}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{32}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{33}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{34}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{35}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{36}	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
J_{37}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{38}	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
J_{39}	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	$\{E_{4,1}\}$	+	+
J_{40}	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{5,2}\}$	+	+
J_{41}^λ	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{4,2}\}$	$\{E_{4,1} - E_{4,2}\}$	+	+

3 Description of local inner derivations on nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras of dimension five

Theorem: Each local inner derivation of the Jordan algebra J_7 is an inner derivation.

Theorem: Each local inner derivation of the five-dimensional Jordan algebras $J_1, J_4, J_5, J_6, J_7, J_8, J_9, J_{10}, J_{11}, J_{12}, J_{13}, J_{14}, J_{15}^\alpha, J_{16}, J_{17}, J_{18}, J_{19}, J_{20}, J_{21}, J_{22}, J_{24}^\gamma, J_{24}^0, J_{24}^{\frac{1}{2}}$,

$\mathcal{J}_{25}, \mathcal{J}_{26}^{\delta}, \mathcal{J}_{26}^0, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{\varepsilon, \phi}, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-1}}, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{-1, -1}, \mathcal{J}_{28}, \mathcal{J}_{29}, \mathcal{J}_{30}, \mathcal{J}_{31}, \mathcal{J}_{32}, \mathcal{J}_{33}, \mathcal{J}_{34}, \mathcal{J}_{35}, \mathcal{J}_{36}, \mathcal{J}_{37}, \mathcal{J}_{38}, \mathcal{J}_{39}, \mathcal{J}_{40}, \mathcal{J}_{41}^{\lambda}$ is an inner derivation.

Theorem: A linear operator on the five-dimensional Jordan algebra \mathcal{J}_2 is a local inner derivation if and only if it has the following form:

$$\text{LocInDer}(\mathcal{J}_2) = \{E_{3,1}, E_{3,4}\}. \quad (3)$$

4 Description of 2-local inner derivations on nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras of dimension five

This section is devoted to the description of 2-local inner derivations of indecomposable five dimensional nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras.

All notations, concerning the Jordan algebras below, are taken from [19] (see table 1).

Theorem: Every 2-local inner derivation on the Jordan algebra \mathcal{J}_2 is an inner derivation.

Theorem: Each 2-local inner derivation of the nilpotent non-associative Jordan algebras $\mathcal{J}_1, \mathcal{J}_2, \mathcal{J}_3, \mathcal{J}_4, \mathcal{J}_5, \mathcal{J}_6, \mathcal{J}_{10}, \mathcal{J}_{11}, \mathcal{J}_{12}, \mathcal{J}_{13}, \mathcal{J}_{14}, \mathcal{J}_{15}^{\alpha}, \mathcal{J}_{22}, \mathcal{J}_{23}^{\beta}, \mathcal{J}_{24}^{\gamma}, \mathcal{J}_{24}^0, \mathcal{J}_{24}^{-\frac{1}{2}}, \mathcal{J}_{25}, \mathcal{J}_{26}^{\delta}, \mathcal{J}_{26}^0, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{\varepsilon, \phi}, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{\varepsilon, \varepsilon^{-1}}, \mathcal{J}_{27}^{-1, -1}, \mathcal{J}_{28}, \mathcal{J}_{29}, \mathcal{J}_{30}, \mathcal{J}_{31}, \mathcal{J}_{32}, \mathcal{J}_{33}, \mathcal{J}_{34}, \mathcal{J}_{35}, \mathcal{J}_{36}, \mathcal{J}_{37}, \mathcal{J}_{38}, \mathcal{J}_{39}, \mathcal{J}_{40}, \mathcal{J}_{41}^{\lambda}$ is an inner derivation.

In the Jordan algebra \mathcal{J}_7 there exists a 2-local inner derivation which is not a derivation.

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